

Code - Switching and Code- Mixing in Chimamanda's *Half of a Yellow Sun*

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Abstract

The paper analyses the twin aspects of Code–Switching and Code–Mixing, and Translation devices in Chimamanda Adichie's *Half of a Yellow Sun* to - evaluate their effectiveness in localizing the text. Pierre Bourdieu's framework on Code Switching and Code Mixing was used to ascertain the pragmalinguistic functions of the devices in the novel. It was found that the devices enabled the author to achieve greater degrees of Foregrounding, Identity, Focusing, Distancing and Neutralization. These pragmalinguistic elements are used creatively to give the text a local taste even though it was presented in English. They also emphasize the fact that as Africans, we can tell our stories as we see and feel them, but painted in the colours of the English language.

Keywords: Code-Mixing, Code-Switching, Identity, Paralinguistics

Résumé

L'article analyse les deux aspects de changement de code et de l'alternance de code et les dispositifs de traduction dans *Half of a Yellow Sun* de Chimamanda Adichie afin d'évaluer leur efficacité dans la localisation du texte. La théorie de Pierre Bourdieu sur le changement de codes et l'alternance de code a été utilisée pour déterminer les fonctions pragmatiques et linguistiques de ces dispositifs dans le roman. Il a été constaté que les dispositifs ont permis à l'auteur d'obtenir la plus grande réussite, en matière d'identité, de mise au premier plan, de mise au point, de distanciation et de neutralisation. Ces éléments pragmatiques et linguistiques sont utilisés de manière créative pour donner au texte la couleur locale même s'il a été présenté en anglais. Ils soulignent également le fait qu'en tant qu'Africains, nous pouvons raconter nos histoires telles que nous les voyons et les ressentons, tout en les habillant en langue anglaise.

Mots-clés: Changement de code, alternance de code, Identité, Paralinguistique

Introduction

In the attempt to make their writings authentic, the writers in Africa, and indeed Nigeria, sometimes employ the twin aspects of Code-Mixing and Code Switching and Translation devices in expressing their views or telling their stories. Code Mixing and Code-Switching (CM/CS) are writing devices which have a social, discursive and referential significance in a text. There has not been a clear consensus however, on the appropriate definitions of CM/CS by language experts.

Gumperz (1982, p 59) defines CS as “the juxtapositions within the same speech exchange of passages of speech belonging to two different grammatical systems or subsystems”. Gumperz Therefore sees CS as a switch between two language codes.

Singh (1985, p. 34) sees Code-Mixing as 'intra-sentential Switching', and uses Code Switching for any diglossic situation where only one Code is employed at a time." In this definition, Singh sees Code-Mixing as the switch in two or more Codes within a sentence boundary, hence "intra", while Code-Switching is used to refer to the switch in Codes between sentences, hence "inter".

Some researchers including Milroy & Muysken (1995) and Ercan Boztepe (2005) have used both concepts, CS/CM as Code-Switching (CS). Therefore, they define CS as "the alternative use by bilinguals of two or more languages in the same conversation", and use Code Switching as a cover term under which different forms of bilingual behaviour are subsumed.

But the position of this paper adopts the views where the concepts are seen as two different sets of linguistic activities; Code Mixing referring to a change within sentence boundaries, and Code-switching, a change outside sentence boundaries.

Poplack (1980) outlines three major types of CS/CM. The list here is: tag-, inter-, intra. Tag-Switching involves the insertion of a tag in one language into an utterance which is otherwise entirely in the other language e.g Mbok_[Please] leave me alone (Efik and English).

Intrasentential Switching involves a switch at a group, clause or sentence boundaries, where each group/clause or sentence is in one language or another. e.g "Sia mudu kaha, I have to go there myself". (Efik/English) (since you will not go, I have to go there myself)

Intersentential Switching involves Switching which occurs between sentence boundaries. E.g. "Eden owo Iyip, we have said ediwak ini, you are the most reliable". (Efik & English). (The man with special strength, we have said many times, you are the most reliable).

The two concepts are commonly used by Nigerian writers to express certain specific functions in social interaction situations, and also some community-specific ways of communicating with one another. Some authors then go further to engage in in-text translations of the codes they use in order to reach a wider audience and create a literary appeal. The meanings and the artistic significance of the 'foreign' items used are revealed to the reader without a deliberate attempt to translate. Bandia says that:

in-text translation is an attempt to clarify the meaning of a local code, expression, clause or sentence within an utterance which is otherwise entirely in the main language of writing or expression. The device is very unique and necessary in their works, because it helps to clarify an utterance within an utterance or a discourse (1996, p. 141).

In Adichie's *Half of a Yellow Sun*, the author presents the story in urbane English but drapes it literarily with indigenous words, groups, clauses and sentences to provide colour and sensibilities of the Nigerian/Ibo society. The reader is sometimes caught in two worlds, the foreign 'imposed' culture, and the local/indigenous culture.

Theoretical Framework

The framework by Pierre Bourdieu (1977a) will be used to analyse the use of the concept (CS/CM) in Adichie's in *Half of a Yellow Sun*. Bourdieu (1977b) observes that "what is called linguistic conflicts arise when the possessors of the dominated competence refuse to recognize the dominant language and with it, the monopoly of linguistic legitimacy" (p. 664). Bourdieu's theory on Code-Mixing and Code-Switching emphasizes five major pragmatolinguistic functions of CS/CM. These are, **Foregrounding:** It is the tendency of the speaker to use a code that appeals to one person. It is a form of re-enforcement.

Identity: It is used to mean the use of language as a means of solidarity, kinship and other types of group membership.

Focusing: It is the use of language to isolate the addressee as the sole intended listener to the utterance in question.

Distance: Distance on its own, is used as a form of saying to the listener, that the message is not meant for him or her

Neutralization: It is the use of mixing and switching to neutralize the effect the message would have if used in another code.

Synopsis of *Half of a Yellow Sun*

The novel, *Half of a Yellow Sun*, afterwards referred to as 'HOAYS', is set in the 1960's Nigeria state. It captures the lives of the major characters, Odenigbo, Olanna, Kainene, Richard and Ugwu in pre, during and post Nigeria civil war period, as they wade through the trauma and the difficulties life throws at them.

The story is cast in three different times, the period of bliss, enthusiasm and hope (before the war), the period of gloom, tribulations and survival (during the war), and the period of awareness uncertainty and seduced hope (after the war). The story reveals that even in times of difficulties and deprivation that is associated with war, there is the essence of humanity, as shown in the love between Odenigbo and Olanna, and in Richard and Kainenes'.

Odenigbo, the main character, is a brilliant Pan- Africanist, who believes the black man should shed the toga of Neo-colonialism and rise to its glory and strength. He is very optimistic of the abilities of the black man to conquer his environment, and so, he constantly rejects any form of indignity, skepticism or hopelessness.

Olanna, his wife, is a smart young independent- minded and affirmative woman, who chooses to teach over a better and privileged lifestyle offered by her father. She prefers hard work, independence, and above all self determined love.

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Kainene, Olanna's twin sister, is an aggressive and talented entrepreneur, who decides to expand the business frontiers of her parents. She is also very independent in thoughts. She decides against all odds to choose a white man over her black Nigerian men as her life partner.

Richard, Kainene's partner, decides to come to Nigeria to rediscover himself and his penchant to write. He falls in love with Kainene and decides to spend the rest of his life in Nigeria and with Kainene.

Ugwu is a young aggressive, inquisitive and brilliant house help to Odenigbo and Olanna. His dream is to be like his 'master' someday. And so he tries determinedly to expand his knowledge in education. A humble, and quick to learn villager, with an explosive appetite for young girls with curvy shapes, was almost made to pay for this passion.

Together, we are able to see through their eyes, the pain, the neglect, the betrayal and abandonment of both the Biafran government and the Nigerian government during and after the war.

The period before the civil war shows the vibrant young men and women of the *intelligentsia* trying to build a society devoid of incompetence and skepticism. This period presents the golden age of Nigeria, where dreams are cast and implemented. The vision of a vibrant young nation is born and the people begin to believe in a new Nigeria

This future is later diminished by the greed and ineptitude of the ruling class, who prepares the ground for the first military coup in Nigeria, and a later counter coup which finally leads to the civil war.

The next period witnesses the destruction of the dream and hopes of the earlier epoch. The people of the South Eastern region, led by Odimegwu Ojukwu decide to secede from Nigeria. This leads to the war that eventually destroyed everything that was built and nurtured. The vibrant lives of the intelligent class and the business class of the people of this region were battered and destroyed by the conquering Nigerian government.

The final stage shows a glimpse of hope, mixed with uncertainty. The war is over physically but it is still psychologically ongoing. The war leaves behind so many bruises. Kainene could not be found. Richard is distraught, Odenigbo's mum is killed, houses and properties destroyed. But as Odenigbo and Olanna return to their home in the University, they provide some flicker of hope and a new beginning, a glimpse perhaps, of just a *Half of a Yellow Sun*.

Instances of Code-Mixing and Code Switching in *Half of a Yellow Sun*

In analyzing the concepts used in the novel, HOAYS, the occurrences will be put in three major structures and analyzed. However, the word level, and the group/clause levels,

will be discussed inclusively. That is both the word and the group will appear under same heading. Most of the indigenous words used in this novel appear within the sentence boundaries, that is, they are inserted at the initial, medial or final position in the sentences. The following are some examples of Code Mixing at the word, group and clause levels.

Foregrounding

1. "I told Master you will leave everything fast, Osiso-Osiso", his aunty said. p. 14.
"Osiso-Osiso" is a word that has a single meaning "fast", but used here as a compound word. It is in line with Nigeria language usage where the issue of redundancy is common. The word is repeated to re-enforce intent or meaning. The pragmalinguistic function of such style is known as foregrounding. It is used for emphasis.
2. You must never behave as if your life belongs to a man. Your life belongs to you and you alone, *Soso gi*. p.276
'*Soso gi*' means "only you" in Igbo. It is used here as *Foregrounding* to re-enforce the seriousness of the message.
3. Yes, but these are better, Fa makali p. 83
"*Fa makali*" means very beautiful. It is used by the author to also re-enforce meaning, or intent. This is another foregrounding.

4. Identity

1. "Rapuba", don't worry about that . p.36.
"Rapuba" means leave it (two words in English)

Olanna, Odenigbo's fiancé, tries to show some form of affinity by introducing the word before mixing English. The function of this use is to show identity, or to establish a form of bond and unity in the household. She asks Ugwu, the house help who was about to open a drink for her to "leave it "*(Rapuba)* while placing her hand over his.

2. It was servants who wiped her *Ike* when she finished shiting. p.125 'Ike' means buttocks. Mama, Odenigbo's mother is trying to establish that Olanna is not suitable for a wife, because she was not raised properly. The author is using this to show the importance of cultural values and how this can affect the attitude of children. Mothers in African culture according to Mama, are responsible for raising their children, not the maids. Here Mama is questioning the role of a maid in an average African home. The mother, she believes, should wipe the child's anus after defecating, not a maid. To her, this is un-african, and a sign of poor upbringing. She is afraid it has affected Olanna, the son's fiancée. This introduces the form of identity.
3. He was now the oldest member of their *Umunna* p.235
"Umunna" means "elders forum"(it means male kins, Nzuko Umunna means kin's Forum, a forum of traditional elders council). This word introduces the culture of the people that build their communities around the elders. The function of this code-mixing is to focus on the relevance of the elders in the community and to show case as it were, the form or style of leadership ascendancy which relies on seniority. This is a form of identity.

4. Uncle Mbaezi had stood up and stamped his foot. *Ndi be anyi*. My people! We will build our own school. p.98

"Ndi be anyi" means "my people". This is a form of translation, an aspect which is integrated in CM/CS, to literarily explain the word or words used in vernacular to a wider audience. Uncle Mbaezi tries to raise the issue of Northern Schools in Nigeria refusing to admit 'Igbo' children. In the process, he uses the 'Igbo' language to call on his people to be aware of what Nigerian government is doing, and to establish a strong identity with his people. The author manipulates this device to drive home the bond and strength in self Identity.

Neutralization

1. You go to *dibia* and you chew it there in front of him. p.97

"*Dibia*" means a native doctor. The author introduces this to highlight the African traditional values and customs, and the belief in such practices. Jomo, Richards gardener is telling Richard about the potency of the herbs the "*dibia*" gave to his sister-in-law who could not be pregnant, but got pregnant after using the herbs. The function of this concept (CM) here is to draw attention to the traditional methods of health practices, which is not accepted by the Western education and civilization. The intention is to neutralize the effect of the word if it were to be said in English.

2. *Na gode!* Thank you, Hajia, Olanna said, wondering how it was possible for people to switch affection of and on, to tie and untie emotions. p. 63.

This is another translation. The expression means "Thank you" in Hausa. -Olanna uses Hausa language here in order to create a sense of neutralization, knowing full well that Mohammed's mother, Hajia, does not like her and would not approve of her son (a Hausa boy) marrying an Igbo girl. The author highlights through this simple code-mixing, the issue of division, and lack of love between these two tribes, and that unity can indeed be achieved between both tribes.

Sentence level

The concept used at this level is mainly code- switching because it occurs across sentence boundaries. Here are some of the structures found in the text.

Focusing

1. "Gowon, what have I done to you? Gowon, *Oke Ihe m mere?*" p.342

During the war, a young woman throws herself down near a child in order to avoid being blown away by the bombs thrown by the Nigerian government. As if she was addressing Gowon, she asks in Igbo, "What did I do to you?" By this the device used is 'focusing'. The woman in the story tries to show that the message is meant for Gowon, and not her people.

2. "*Ana emekwa?*" He asked, eager to speak first." How is life in the North?" p.170

The Igbo language used here in code- switching, meaning "are things going well?" This is an interrogative simple sentence. Richard, the Briton, Kainene's friend opens the

conversation with Madu, an old acquaintance of Kainene, and who Richard suspects is still having an affair with Kainene. By opening the conversation in Igbo instead of English, the author tries to re-introduce the concept of neutralization, and of affiliation. Richard tries to show that he is part of the family, and by using 'igbo', the effect of their meeting is neutralized

3 "We are all Biafrans! *Anyincha Ba Biafra!*" p.389.

The author translates what is said in the first sentence in English into Igbo in the next sentence. Kainene walks up and slaps a pregnant woman who abuses a doctor in the hospital, and repeating those words as a form of foregrounding to show seriousness. The author shows the situation where the Igbos had started suspecting people who were not Igbo and tagging them Saboteurs. Kainene attempts to fight this and gets everyone together in unity.

4 "Ugwuanyi", she said, "you have to come home. *Oga gi Kwanu?* Where is your master?" p.112

Ugwu's family member comes in from the village with anxiety, and informs Ugwu that his presence is needed back home. After speaking in Igbo, she translates into English. It is a form of re-enforcing the import of the message through the use of *Foregrounding*, but the author uses this translation method to ease reading, while at the same time establishing the ethnic colouration of the story.

Many other code- switches used in this text re-enforce the twin aspects of foregrounding and translation. Instances are numerous;

- (i) "Yes, *Chukwu du anyi*". God led us. p. 21
- (ii) "*Madu!* Is this you? *Ogidi Ife a*". p. 174
- (iii) "*Auyi aga fuela!* We have crossed the River Niger". p. 174
- (iv) "*Ekwuzikwananu nofu!* Don't say that". p.239
- (v) "Where are you going? *Ebeka I na eje?*" p. 336

These and many more are the instances where the author alternates between the issues of fidelity in translation, and re-enforcement of intent through the pragmalinguistic function of foregrounding. Through the instrument of translation, the author is able to establish the local content of the story, by introducing the cultural and the traditional elements of the people, and translating them in English to have a wider readership. In some instances, the author employs neutralization, to say things which would not have been said exactly and with the same intensity. This she does by using code-mixing to introduce a word in Ibo that would give a clearer and deeper meaning than any other code may have done. With these concepts, the writer has also used the instrument of identity to create closer bonds and a sense of ownership. By code- mixing, the issues of identity, partnership and struggle are addressed effectively in the story.

Instances of 'distance' are not common. The reason may be that many of the major characters are Ibos, and those who are not, understand the language as well.

This type of code-mixing, and code-switching practised by some African writers according to Bondia (1996) ... are not particularly intrusive for readers.

The author's European language of writing in which they are found does not often appear to have suffered any major violation of its lexico-grammatical structure. The reason for this is that the native words and expression are usually used in such a way that they fit in with the syntactic and grammatical characteristics of the European language. p.144

Conclusion

Writers of African decent use native words and expressions in their works as a means of achieving relevance, authenticity, and local colour without necessarily modifying the grammatical structures of the language of writing. This, Adichie has achieved so well, that the reader cannot miss the flair, and the style of the grammar in use, but at the same time, cannot lose the scent and coloration of the native language, that she has so creatively embedded in the expressions to create seemingly borderless structures that make for delightful reading. One has a feeling of being between two different worlds pulling at him for attention and recognition, but not doing enough to make him feel alien to either. The concepts of code-mixing and code-switching indeed act as bridges in linking the world views of Britain and Nigeria and helping to make each understand the other much more deeply.

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